

Bacterial communities shift and influence in an acid mine drainage treatment using barium carbonate disperse alkaline substrate system

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Abstract

Chemical passive treatment systems used to remediate acid mine drainage has been evaluated based mainly on the reactivity of the chemical alkaline reagents, overlooking the activity of the microorganisms that proliferate in these artificial ecosystems. In this study, the bacterial communities of a passive treatment system known as BDAS (Barium carbonate Dispersed Alkaline Substrate) were investigated using 16S rRNA gene metagenomic sequencing combined with hydrochemical characterization of the AMD and phenotypic characterization of biogenic precipitates. According to the hydrochemical characterization, the water quality improved as the water progressed through the system, with a drastic increase in the pH (up to alkaline conditions) and total organic carbon, as well as the removal of main contaminants such as Ca^{2+} , SO_4^{2-} , Fe^{3+} , Al^{3+} and Mn^{2+} . These environmental changes resulted in an increase in bacterial diversity (richness) during the treatment and in the shift of the bacterial communities from chemoautotrophs (e.g., *Ferrovum* and *Acidiphilum*) to chemoheterotrophs (e.g., *Brevundimonas* and *Geobacter*). Some of these taxa harbour potential to immobilize metals, aiding in the treatment of the water. One of the mechanisms involved in the

immobilization of metals is microbially induced calcium carbonate precipitation, which seems to occur spontaneously in BDAS System. The production of biofilm was also observed in most parts of the system, except in the inlet, helping with the removal of metals. However, in the long run, the build-up of biofilm and precipitation of metals could clog (i.e., biofouling) the pores of the matrix, reducing the treatment efficiency. Potential human pathogens (e.g., *Legionella*) were also detected in BDAS indicating the need for a treatment step at the end of the system to remove pathogenic microorganisms. These findings present a new perspective of the bacterial communities and their effects (both positively and negatively) in a chemical passive treatment system.

Keywords: chemical passive treatment system, shift of the bacterial communities, metal immobilization and Biofouling and pathogens.

Highlights:

- Bacterial communities shift and influence in a chemical passive treatment system.
- Immobilization of metals by microbially induced calcium carbonate precipitation (MICP).
- Bacterial biofouling might compromise the porosity of the organic matrix of the reactors.
- The relative abundance of potential human pathogens increased through the systems.

1. Introduction

The mining industry is the foundation of many emerging and developing economies globally. However, the generation of mining waste leads to the production of leachates mostly enriched in toxic metals (e.g., Al^{3+} , As^{3-} , and Pb^{2+}), which is considered one of the leading environmental concerns worldwide (Chen et al., 2021; Tong et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2021). Mining leachates such as acid mine drainage (AMD) are generated by sulphide-mineral (mainly pyrite) oxidation mediated by atmospheric oxygen, water, and microbial activity in mining wastes. These drainages can reach surface and groundwater sources and rapidly deteriorate the quality of water due to high concentrations of sulphate, heavy metals (i.e., Cd^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , and Co^{2+}) and low pH (2-4) (Chen et al., 2021; Skousen et al., 2019).

The need to remediate AMD has become a focus of many researchers (Chen et al., 2020; She et al., 2021; Song et al., 2022). The remediation methods for AMD can be broadly classified as active (e.g., membrane systems such as reverse osmosis) and passive systems (e.g., dispersed alkaline substrate (DAS)). Passive systems are more frequently used for decommissioned mines due to their low cost and maintenance (Chen et al., 2021; Tong et al., 2020). One of the most promising passive technologies has been the dispersed alkaline substrate (DAS) water treatment system (Younger et al., 2002). This system uses alkaline (calcite or magnesite) and organic material such as wood shavings as a matrix (Skousen et al., 2019) to remediate AMD. Due to the high concentrations of sulphate in AMD, a variation of the DAS system was developed, using barium carbonate (BaCO_3) as alkaline reagent, to promote the precipitation of sulphate into BaSO_4 not achieved with other alkaline reagents (Gomez-Arias et al., 2015; Torres et al., 2018). The BDAS system, as it is known this AMD passive treatment systems, increases the pH to 8-9 (alkaline conditions), precipitating divalent metals such as Zn^{2+} and Mn^{2+} (Torres et al., 2018), as well as salts such as Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} as carbonate neoformed minerals, which induce even the incorporation of Na^+ , Cl^- , and SO_4^{2-} (Kitano et al., 1975).

Extremophiles in AMD such as *Acidithiobacillus ferroxidans*, which can accelerate the Fe^{2+} oxidation up to 10^6 times (Kirby et al., 1999), have been used as bioremediation agents in natural Fe-oxidizing lagoon (NFOL) to remove Fe^{2+} as Fe^{3+} oxide-hydroxide, which in turn induce the co-precipitation of trivalent and divalent metals such as Al^{3+} ,

Cu²⁺ and Pb²⁺, among others (Macías et al., 2012). *Desulfovibrio* (sulphate reducing bacteria (SRB)) and *Pseudomonas* have also been isolated from AMD, enriched, and used in passive AMD bioremediation strategies such as Rapid Alkalinisation Producing Systems (RAPS) (RoyChowdhury et al., 2015), sulphate reducing reactors (Macingova and Luptakova, 2012) and recently, inducing carbonate precipitation in experiments at bench-scale (Bai et al., 2017).

However, those indigenous microorganisms that naturally inhabit AMD may negatively impact the AMD treatment systems if they proliferate excessively forming biofilms, which can lead, like in the case of reverse osmosis, to undesirable membrane clogging, known as 'biofouling' (Sánchez, 2018). Therefore, it is reasonable to think that indigenous microorganisms from AMD might also colonize chemical passive water treatments and cause clogging (Zhao et al. 2009). A few studies have documented the microbial distribution and shifts throughout neutralization processes (Chen et al., 2020; Ly et al., 2019; Ramos-Perez et al., 2022; Valkanas, 2018). However, the microbial shifts throughout the alkalinization processes and their impact (negative or positive) on these chemical passive treatment systems such as BDAS is still unknown. Indeed, no evidence of bacterially induced carbonate biomineralization processes within the chemical passive systems has been elucidated to date. In addition, most studies focus on the removal of inorganic compounds, overlooking the biological contamination (i.e., the presence of pathogens species in the water released) that could be promoted by these passive systems (Chen et al., 2020; Ly et al., 2019; Ramos-Perez et al., 2022; Valkanas, 2018). Altogether these factors might influence the efficiency of passive chemical water treatment systems and the quality of the treated water.

Here, we aim to characterize the bacterial communities in an AMD passive treatment system (i.e., BDAS system) using targeted metagenomic 16S rRNA Illumina sequencing. In addition, hydrochemical and phenotypic analyses will provide insights into the contribution of these microorganisms to the mobilization of metals and the clogging of the system through biofilm formation. Finally, this study brings forth insights on the biological contamination generated by the BDAS system.

2. Materials and Methods

Treatment system description and sample collection

The Barium Carbonate Disperse Alkaline Substrate (BDAS) treatment system under study consists of 5-units (**Fig. 1**). Briefly, the AMD flows gravitationally throughout the system starting at the Inlet (S1). The AMD then flows into the reactor containing calcite mixed with an organic matrix (wood shaving) (S2), where it becomes neutralized and trivalent metals such as Fe^{3+} and Al^{3+} precipitate as oxyhydroxysulphate. The neutralized water then flows through the reactor containing barium carbonate (BaCO_3) mixed with an organic matrix (wood shaving) (S3), where the water is alkalinized. Simultaneously, sulphate and divalent metals (e.g., Zn^{2+} and Mn^{2+}), as well as salts (e.g., Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+}), are immobilized as BaSO_4 and neoformed carbonate minerals, respectively (van Heerden et al., 2016). The water then flows through the decanter (S4) and the cascade (S5). The decanter contributes to the settling of big particles that come from the reactors, whereas the function of the cascade is to oxygenate the water (van Heerden et al., 2016). Interestingly, both the decanter and the cascade show proliferation of biofilm-like material. This patented technology (National patent number P49198ZAPO and International patent number WO2016035045) can remove up to 90% of the SO_4^{2-} , 98 to 99% of the Fe^{3+} , and 90% of the Ca^{2+} . The treatment is effective even in the removal of Sr^{2+} (92%) > Mg^{2+} (22%) > K^+ (8%) > Na^+ (8%). The Ba^{2+} concentrations (0.1 mg/L) never exceed the limits of WHO (1.3 mg/L) for drinking water, while the EC and TDS decreased around 25 to 30% depending on the inlet treatment efficiency. This system has been implemented at pilot scale in South Africa and Wales (Roetting et al., 2021) and has been tested at bench scale in Spain (Torres et al., 2018) and Chile (Larraguibel et al., 2020).

In this study, water samples (some containing biofilm in suspension) were collected in 50 mL conical tubes and 5 L sterile carboys. Three replicate samples were taken from every unit of the BDAS system located nearby Carolina town in Mpumalanga (South Africa) (26°13'17.51" S - 29°58'05.72" E). The samples were transported to the laboratory in cooler boxes and stored at 4 °C until analyzes were performed.

Fig. 1: BDAS on-site with the system design. As depicted in subset images, biofilms were observed in the calcite and barium carbonate reactors.

Hydrochemical characterisation

Physicochemical parameters such as pH, Electrical Conductivity (EC), Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), redox potential (Eh) and temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) were measured on-site using ExStix®II multi-probe (Extech Instruments, USA) and an ExStix®II Eh probe (Extech Instruments, USA). Eh measurements were corrected accordingly to Standard Hydrogen Electrode (SHE). Moreover, SO_4^{2-} , Fe^{2+} and Fe_{Total} concentrations were analyzed on-site using a HACH spectrophotometer (model DR/900 colorimeter) according to the colorimetric methods described in the HACH Procedures Manual (Method Sulphate 608, Method Ferrous iron 255 and FerroVer 265, respectively). The elemental composition (i.e., K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , Be^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Fe^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Cr^{2+} , U^{4+} , V^{3+} , Mo^{6+} , Sr^{2+} , Se^{2-} , Si^{4+}) was determined from 50 mL aliquots of water filtered through a $0.45\ \mu\text{m}$ (Whatman®) cellulose filters and acidified to a $\text{pH} < 2$ with HNO_3 onsite. Thereafter, the samples were analyzed by Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) (NexION2000-PerkinElmer) by the Institute for Ground Water Studies (IGS) (University of the Free State). Sulphide concentrations were

determined using the methylene blue method according to the 143-procedure described by Fonselius et al. (2007).

Characterisation of the bacterial communities

DNA extraction

Water samples (1L) were vacuum-filtered through sterile 0.2 µm cellulose disc filter papers (PALL corporations, USA) to concentrate microbial cells. Half of each filter was cut into small pieces using a sterile surgical blade inside a laminar flow for DNA extraction. These pieces were placed into 2 mL tubes, and environmental DNA (eDNA) was extracted using a NucleoSpin® Soil DNA Isolation Kit (Macherey-Nagel™, Germany) following the manufacturer's protocol. eDNA concentrations were quantified using a Nanodrop spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific, USA), and the integrity of the eDNA was assessed using electrophoresis on 1% agarose gel with GelRed™ (Anatech, South Africa). Finally, the eDNA of high quality and purity was stored at -20 °C and shipped to Mr DNA (www.mrdnalab.com, USA) for sequencing.

16S rRNA amplicon sequencing

The sequencing was performed on an Illumina Miseq platform. The 16S rRNA gene region V3 and V4 was amplified using the universal primer pair 515F (5'-GTGCAGCMGCCGCGGTAA-3') and 806R (5'-GGACTACVGGGTTCTAAT-3') (Caporaso et al., 2011). PCR reactions were carried out in a total volume of 25 µL comprising of 25 ng DNA template, 1.5 µL (0.3 µM) of each primer, 12.5 µL KAPA HiFi HotStart Ready-mix (1X) (ROCHE, South Africa) and 7 µL nuclease-free water (WhiteSci, South Africa). The PCR consisted of an initial denaturation step at 94 °C for 3 minutes, followed by 30 cycles of regular denaturation at 94 °C for 30 seconds, 53 °C for 40 seconds and 72 °C for 1 minute, with the final elongation step at 72 °C for 5 minutes. The PCR products were checked on a 1% agarose gel with GelRed™ (Anatech, South Africa), followed by purification using calibrated Ampure XP beads. The purified products were used to prepare a DNA library following the Illumina TruSeq DNA library preparation protocol.

Bioinformatics and statistical analysis

The raw amplicon sequence data was processed in QIIME 2 version 2022.2 (Bolyen et al., 2018). Shortly, the raw sequence data were first demultiplexed, quality filtered

based on the Phred score values (>30) and denoised using DADA2 to create amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) (Callahan et al., 2016). After training the classifier, ASVs were taxonomically assigned using the Naïve Bayes Classifier (Bokulich et al., 2018a) against the SILVA_132_99% reference database (McDonald et al., 2011). The resulting taxonomy and ASVs tables were imported in RStudio (R Core Team, 2013) and merged into a “phyloseq” object (McMurdie and Holmes, 2013) for downstream analysis.

a. Bacterial α -diversity

The ASV abundance table was rarefied to 11,127 sequences per sample to account for differences in library sizes across samples. Chao1 estimator and Observed and Shannon diversity index were measured using the “trans_alpha” function within the “microeco” package (Liu, 2022). ANOVA and post-hoc Tukey were used to determine statistical differences in α -diversity between units. In addition, the unique and shared ASVs were visualized as a Venn diagram using the packages “Venn” and “Venn diagram” (Duşa, 2022).

b. Bacterial β -diversity

The “microeco” package was also used to analyze bacterial β -diversity (Liu et al., 2022). The compositional dissimilarity between different communities was measured using Bray-Curtis distances using the “trans_beta” function. Dissimilarities between communities were further visualized using Principal Coordinates Analysis (PCoA). The significant taxa differentiating the community across units were analyzed using the function “trans_diff” in “microeco” based on ANOVA method. Redundancy analysis (RDA) using the “trans_env” class were used to infer the environmental factors affecting bacterial community structure.

c. Chemical analysis

The differences in the hydrochemistry were visualized using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with Euclidean distances. ANOVA and post-hoc Tukey test within the package “stats” (R Core Team, 2013) were used to determine statistical differences in chemistry between the different units.

Electron microscopy and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) analysis.

Half filter containing cells and biofilm debris was removed and prepared for scanning electron microscopy energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDS) and Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy analysis. For SEM-EDS, the samples were fixed in 0.1 M (pH 7.0) sodium phosphate-buffered glutardialdehyde (3%) for at least 3 hours, followed by 1-hour fixation in similarly buffered osmium tetroxide (1%). The samples were then collected on 0.2 μ M polycarbonate membrane filters and dehydrated in a graded ethanol series (50%, 70% and 95% for 20 minutes in each phase, followed by two changes of 100% for 1 hour in each phase). The samples were then dried using a critical point dryer (Tousimis, Maryland, U.S.A.) and mounted on stubs (Cambridge pin type, 10 mm) using double-sided carbon tape and gold-coated (\pm 60 nm) with a Bio-Rad sputter coater (United Kingdom). Then, they were analyzed with a JSM-7800F Extreme-resolution Analytical Field Emission SEM-EDS (Tokyo, Japan) at the Centre for Microscopy (University of the Free State). The remaining half of the halved filters obtained from the cell concentrations of each unit (S1 – S5) were frozen at -80 °C and lyophilised using a Freeze dryer (Bruker Tensor 27 model, Germany) overnight to avoid oxidation processes. Functional groups in the lyophilised cell content were then identified using Fourier transform infrared FT-IR spectroscopy. At the same time, the spectral analysis was done in the mid-IR region (500 – 4000 cm^{-1}) with an average 16 scans. The peaks from the data were identified using previously reported data.

4. Results and discussion

Chemical treatment processes

The water to be treated by the BDAS system presented typical hydrochemical characteristics of AMD; acidic (pH < 5), mesophilic (29 °C) and oxidative conditions (0.196 mg/L of dissolved oxygen (DO) and 479.86 mV) with high conductivity (EC) values (2013.3 mS/cm) (Equeenuddin et al., 2010; Zuberer and Zibilske, 2021) (Table 1 or Supplementary Figure 1). After flowing through the calcite (S2) and barium (S3) reactors, the pH increased from 4 to 8.41 (Tukey test between S1-S2, S1-S3 and S2-S3 ($p < 0.05$)) while remaining constant through the decanter (S4) and cascade (S5) (Tukey test between S3-S4, S4-S5 and S3-S5 P value; $p > 0.05$). Oxidative conditions were detected throughout the system. Though the DO decreased to microoxic conditions (0.03 mg/L) in the reactors (Tukey test between S1-S2 and S1-S3; $p < 0.05$)

and returned to oxic conditions in the cascade (Tukey test between S1-S4 and S1-S5; $p < 0.05$). TOC (Total Organic Carbon) increased dramatically throughout the system due to the organic matrix in the S2 and S3 ($p < 0.05$). Comparable results were observed in BDAS reactors in a bench scale study by Castillo et al. (2015). An opposite trend was observed in EC due to the removal of SO_4^{2-} , Ca^{2+} , and heavy metals ($p < 0.05$; multiple comparison with ANOVA). The detailed spatial evolution of water chemistry can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Average hydrochemical characteristics. The parameters are as follows; Temp: Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), pH, EC: Electrical Conductivity (mS/cm), Eh: Oxidative Reduction Potential (mV), DO Dissolved Oxygen (g/L), TOC: Total Organic Carbon (g/L).

Units	Physicochemical parameters											
	Temp ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)		pH		EC (mS/cm)		Eh (mV)		DO (g/L)		TOC (g/L)	
	$n = 3$		$n = 3$		$n = 3$		$n = 3$		$n = 3$		$n = 3$	
	Mean	\pm SE	Mean	\pm SE	Mean	\pm SE	Mean	\pm SE	Mean	\pm SE	Mean	\pm SE
Inlet	26.13	$\pm 0.31^a$	4.24	$\pm 0.05^a$	2013.33	$\pm 9.07^a$	479.87	$\pm 3.96^a$	0.20	$\pm 0.01^a$	1.07	$\pm 0.04^a$
Calcite	22.17	$\pm 0.12^b$	6.45	$\pm 0.05^b$	1929.67	$\pm 29.94^b$	-63.00	$\pm 1.57^b$	0.03	$\pm 0.00^a$	2.24	$\pm 0.14^a$
Barium	24.47	$\pm 0.32^c$	8.41	$\pm 0.11^b$	554.67	$\pm 22.23^c$	-49.60	$\pm 1.18^c$	0.02	$\pm 0.00^b$	6.77	$\pm 0.04^b$
Decanter	25.53	$\pm 0.32^c$	8.14	$\pm 0.13^c$	550.67	$\pm 5.13^c$	-131.78	$\pm 1.45^d$	0.02	$\pm 0.00^b$	5.83	$\pm 0.11^b$
Cascade	22.80	$\pm 0.44^c$	8.23	$\pm 0.11^d$	540.33	$\pm 1.53^c$	-85.94	$\pm 3.36^e$	0.18	$\pm 0.03^b$	5.97	$\pm 0.09^b$

*SE: standard error.

Different letters indicate significant differences (based on ANOVA and post-hoc Tukey test, $p < 0.05$) between the hydrochemical characteristics of the system's units.

In particular, the removal of major elements such as Ca^{2+} and SO_4^{2-} occur in the barium reactor (S3) (Tukey test between S2 and S3 < 0.05), while elements such as Ba^{2+} and Mg^{2+} remain in solution throughout the system without significant variation (Table 2 or Supplementary Figure 2). It is worth mentioning that the concentration of major and minor elements measured in the treated water were within the limit established by WHO for drinking water (World Health Organization, 2022).

Table 2: Average Elemental composition in (g/L) from every reactor.

Units	Major elements			Minor elements						
	<i>n</i> = 3	<i>n</i> = 3	<i>n</i> = 3	<i>n</i> = 3	<i>n</i> = 3	<i>n</i> = 3	<i>n</i> = 3	<i>n</i> = 3	<i>n</i> = 3	<i>n</i> = 3
	Mean ± SE	Mean ± SE	Mean ± SE	Mean ± SE	Mean ± SE	Mean ± SE	Mean ± SE	Mean ± SE	Mean ± SE	Mean ± SE
	Mg ²⁺	Ca ²⁺	SO ₄ ²⁻	Fe ²⁺	Fe _{Total}	Al ³⁺	Mn ²⁺	Ba ²⁺	Sr ²⁺	Pb ²⁺
Inlet	0.13 ± 0.10 ^a	4.62 ± 0.30 ^a	7.27 ± 0.03 ^a	0.08 ± 0.01 ^a	0.49 ± 0.01 ^a	0.61 ± 0.05 ^a	0.01 ± 0.02 ^a	0.00 ± 0.00 ^a	0.02 ± 0.00 ^a	0.08 ± 0.01 ^a
Calcite	0.09 ± 0.06 ^a	6.46 ± 0.70 ^b	7.21 ± 0.07 ^a	0.03 ± 0.00 ^b	0.10 ± 0.01 ^b	0.01 ± 0.00 ^b	0.05 ± 0.00 ^b	0.00 ± 0.00 ^{ab}	0.02 ± 0.01 ^a	0.00 ± 0.00 ^b
Barium	0.08 ± 0.01 ^a	1.41 ± 0.07 ^c	0.32 ± 0.00 ^b	0.00 ± 0.00 ^c	0.01 ± 0.00 ^c	0.01 ± 0.00 ^b	0.00 ± 0.00 ^b	0.01 ± 0.01 ^b	0.01 ± 0.00 ^b	0.00 ± 0.00 ^b
Decanter	0.08 ± 0.01 ^a	1.28 ± 0.02 ^c	0.06 ± 0.05 ^c	0.00 ± 0.00 ^c	0.00 ± 0.00 ^c	0.01 ± 0.00 ^b	0.00 ± 0.00 ^b	0.00 ± 0.01 ^b	0.01 ± 0.00 ^b	0.00 ± 0.00 ^b
Cascade	0.10 ± 0.05 ^a	1.13 ± 0.09 ^c	0.03 ± 0.00 ^c	0.00 ± 0.00 ^c	0.00 ± 0.00 ^c	0.01 ± 0.01 ^b	0.00 ± 0.00 ^b	0.00 ± 0.00 ^b	0.01 ± 0.00 ^b	0.00 ± 0.00 ^b

*SE: standard error.

Different letters indicate significant differences (based on ANOVA and post-hoc Tukey test, $p < 0.05$) between the hydrochemical characteristics of the system's units.

According to a PCA (**Fig. 2**), three groups consisting of samples from the (i) inlet (S1), (ii) calcite reactor (S2) and (iii) BaCO₃ reactor (S3), decanter (S4) and cascade (S5) were observed, indicating the stabilization of the treated water throughout the last three units. In the PCA graphic for variables (**Fig. 2 PCA-individuals**), it is observed that the pH, heavy metals, and salts, including SO₄²⁻, have a favourable loading in PCA1, which explains 60.9% of the total variance. The PCA2 explains 19.8% of the total variance that Mg²⁺, Ba²⁺, Temp, DO, and TOC strongly influence.

In **Fig. 2 (PCA-variables)**, pH correlated negatively with heavy metals and SO₄²⁻, while a positive correlation between Eh and minor elements (i.e., Fe^{2+/3+}, Al³⁺ and Pb²⁺), and EC and major elements (i.e., Ca²⁺ and SO₄²⁻) are observed. The removal of Ca²⁺ and SO₄²⁻ clearly influence the EC values in the system. However, Eh does not explain the precipitation of minor elements, as Eh would be influenced only by the species with redox properties (e.g., Fe^{2+/3+}). Thus, the precipitation of minor elements should be influenced mainly by the precipitation of Fe³⁺ oxyhydroxysulphates that act as a

sink for these metals (Pérez-Lopéz et al., 2010). The precipitation of carbonate minerals under alkaline conditions in the barium reactor could also act as a sink for Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} (Temmam et al., 2000).

Fig. 2: Principal Component Analysis (PCA) plots for the hydrochemical characteristics to explore and visualize dissimilarities between water samples. The left-hand image shows the samples grouped according to the physicochemical conditions, while the right-hand image shows the relationships between the environmental variables.

Bacterial diversity and structure through the system

A total of 165,915 high-quality reads remained after the filtering process. These reads resulted in the identification of 4,357 Amplicon Sequence Variants (ASVs). Rarefaction curves (Supplementary Figure 3), Chao1, and Good's coverage (~0.99) estimate suggest that the sampling was adequate to cover most of the bacterial diversity in the system. The observed number of variants and the Shannon index indicate a dramatic increase in the bacterial diversity once the AMD went through the reactors and a neutralization process occurred (Tukey test between S1-S2/S3/S4/S5; $p > 0.01$) (**Fig. 3**).

Fig. 3: Alpha diversity measures of the ASVs from BDAS of every unit. Different letters indicate significant differences (based on ANOVA and post-hoc Tukey test, $p < 0.05$) between the measures from each unit of the system.

Likewise in the PCA-Individuals, the PCoA distinguishes 3 clusters (S1, S2 and S3-S4-S5) well differentiated from each other, correlating with the pattern observed or the water chemistry. This supports the idea that the chemistry of the water (especially the pH) shaped the bacterial community structure and composition (**Fig. 4**).

Fig. 4: Principal coordinate analysis (based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarities) displaying differences in community composition. Bacterial communities of the barium (S3), decanter (S4) and cascade (S5) units are more like each other than the Inlet (S1) and calcite communities (S2).

The differential abundance test confirms that the neutralization and alkalinization of the AMD throughout the system shapes the bacterial composition (**Fig. 5**). At phylum level, most ASVs belonged to Proteobacteria, averaging 53.3% of the total number of reads, and were especially abundant in the inlet (Tukey test between S1-S2/S3/S4/S5; $p < 0.05$; S2-S3-S4-S5, $p > 0.05$). When the AMD is neutralized, the relative abundance of the phylum Bacteroidetes increased exponentially becoming the second most abundant phylum (26.38%) in the system (Tukey test between S1-S2/S3/S4/S5, $p < 0.05$; S2-S3-S4-S5, $p > 0.05$). The predominance of Proteobacteria and Bacteroidetes has been observed in other AMD treatment system using limestone as neutralizing reagent (Ramos-Perez et al., 2022). *Verrucomicrobia* (4.59%) and *Spirochaetes* (3.9%) also increased in abundance once the neutralization process occurs (Tukey test between S1-S2, $p < 0.05$). These two phyla were more predominant in S2 (Tukey test between S2-S3, $p < 0.05$; S3-S4-S5; $p = 0.005$). The phylum Firmicutes displayed a similar trend except it was not predominant in S2 (Tukey test between S2-S3-S4-S5; $p > 0.05$). It seems that the alkalinization process

only boosted the growth of phyla Latescibacteria and Cyanobacteria (Tukey test between S2-S3/S4/S5; $p < 0.05$).

At genus level, the ASVs were more variable in abundance throughout the units (reactors) (**Fig. 5**). The most important and abundant genera differentiating the units were *Ferrovum*, *Acidiphilum* and *sulfuriferula* in S1 (Tukey test between S1-S2/S3/S4/S5, $p < 0.05$), *Hydrothalea* in S2 (Tukey test between S2-S1/S3/S4/S5, $p < 0.05$), *Azospirillum*, *Methyloversatilis* and *Novosphingobium* were genera dominating the S3 (Tukey test between S3-S1/S2/S4/S5, $p < 0.05$) and *Lentimicrobium*, *Geobacter* and *Trepomena* in decanter and cascade (Tukey test between S4/S5-S1/S2/S3, $p < 0.05$).

Members of the genera *Ferrovum*, *Acidiphilum* and *Sulfuriferula* are chemolithotrophs associated with the oxidation of Fe^{2+} or S^0 (Coupland and Johnson, 2008; Grettenberger et al., 2020; Malki et al., 2008; Watanabe et al., 2014), while most of the bacterial taxa found in S2, S3, S4, and S5 are facultative or obligate anaerobic chemoorganotrophs associated with fermentation pathways (Albuquerque et al., 2020; Grettenberger et al., 2020; Kalyuzhnaya et al., 2006; Smalley et al., 2015; Steenhoudt and Vanderleyden, 2000); except for members of the genus *Geobacter* that use inorganic compounds (e.g., Fe^{3+}) as electron acceptors (Morgado and Salgueiro, 2022).

The shift of bacterial metabolisms from chemolithotrophs to chemoheterotrophs in the reactors is related to the increase of the bioavailability of total organic carbon due to the organic matrix in S2 (Calcite reactor) and S3 (Barium reactor) and the change from oxic to microoxic conditions. It has been suggested that the wood shavings used in some AMD passive treatment systems might serve as a carbon source for chemoheterotrophic bacteria (Skousen et al., 2016). In addition, It cannot be ruled out that some of these bacteria (e.g., *Azospirillum* and *Novosphingobium*) might be introduced by the organic matrix (i.e., wood shaving) due to their association with plants (Steenhoudt and Vanderleyden, 2000; Viruega-Góngora et al., 2020). Ultimately the increase in pH is the main driver of the increase in bacterial alpha diversity in this system as found previously (Ramos-Perez et al., 2022; She et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2020).

Fig. 5: The most important and abundant phylum and genera differentiating the units. Right image – Relative abundance at phylum level. Left image - Relative abundance at genus level. Different letters indicate significant differences (based on ANOVA and post-hoc Tukey test, $p < 0.05$) between the phyla and genera.

Bacterial taxa associated with the immobilisation of metals

The distance-based redundancy analysis (db-RDA) reveals a positive correlation between the genera *Acidiphilium* and *Ferroplasma* and minor elements (e.g., Al^{3+} , Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+}), SO_4^{2-} , EC and Eh (**Fig. 6**). These acidophiles and Fe^{2+} oxidizers colonized the Inlet and likely catalyzed the precipitation of Fe^{3+} oxyhydroxysulphate (e.g., schwertmannite) that functioned as a sink for trivalent and divalent metals such as Al^{3+} and Pb^{2+} (Carrero et al., 2015; Luef et al., 2012). Indeed, precipitates of schwertmannite like-structures (**Fig. 7A**) were observed in S1. Similar neoformed minerals were observed in AMD related environments (She et al., 2021; Tischler et al., 2013). The removal of metals correlated positively with the drop of conductivity (EC), and the occurrence of Fe^{2+} oxidizers with the oxidative conditions present in this unit (S1).

It appears that *Acidiphilum* and *Ferrovum* were in planktonic phase as biofilm formation was not observed in this unit (S1), despite that these genera are able to produce extracellular polysaccharides (Johnson et al., 2014; Liu et al., 2011). The removal of metals correlated positively with the drop in conductivity (EC), and the occurrence of Fe^{2+} oxidizers with the oxidative conditions present in this unit (**Fig. 6**).

Fig. 6. Redundancy analysis (RDA) plot displays the relationships between different bacterial genera and environmental parameters within the BDAS system. The arrow length represents the strength of the correlation between the environmental variables and the bacteria. The longer the arrow length, the stronger the correlation. The perpendicular distance between bacteria and environmental variable axes in the plot reflects their correlations. The smaller the distance, the stronger the correlation. Samples are colour coded according to the units; blue – Inlet, orange – calcite reactor, purple – barium reactor, pink – decanter, green – cascade.

Unlike the inlet, the neoformed minerals in the calcite reactor seem to be encapsulated in biofilms (**Fig. 7B**). Members of the genus *Hydrotalea* have not been associated with the immobilization of metals or biofilm production (Albuquerque et al., 2020). However, *Brevundimonas*, one of the most abundant and prevalent genera in the units, especially in S2 (calcite reactor) (**Supplementary Figure 4 and Supplementary Table 2**), might be responsible for EPS production. It has been reported that members

belonging to the genus *Brevundimonas* could act synergistically with *Azospirillum*, *Hydrothalea*, and *Novosphingobium* creating a more resistant biofilm under high concentrations of metals and salts (Kumar et al., 2015). *Brevundimonas* also produces a more resistant biofilm under higher concentrations of Ca^{2+} exposure (Angoshtari et al., 2020), such as in S2.

Many studies suggest that EPS serves as a matrix for the adsorption of metals (Richard et al., 2019; Qiongjie et al., 2022; Zhu et al., 2016). The EPS matrix contains both “hard” (e.g., carboxylic, and phenolic) and “soft” (e.g., amides and amines) complexing sites for metals and salts (Liu and Fang, 2002; Zhu et al., 2012). Indeed, the analysis by FT-IR of the biofilm debris from the filter revealed peaks attributed to amides, amines (1633 cm^{-1}) and phospholipids (1730.04 cm^{-1}), which might act as complexing sites inducing the immobilization of metals (**Supplementary Figure 5 and Table 3**).

Fig. 7. Scanning electron micrographs overlaid with the electron dispersive spectra indicate the elements present in the samples. A) – Sample from the Inlet (S1) displays neofomed minerals composed of mainly Fe and Ca and O. B) Sample from calcite reactor (S2) show neofomed mineral encapsulated by a biofilm-like structure. C) – Barium reactor (S3) sample displays minerals composed mainly of Ba and SO_4^{2-} and biofilm-like structure in the background. D) and E) (S4) suggests the formation of neofomed minerals of Ca, C and O encapsulating rod-shaped bacterioforms in the decanter. F) Sample from the cascade (S5) show bacterioforms and biofilm-like structure.

Bacteria dominating the units S2, S3, S4 and S5 (i.e., *Methyloversatilis*, *Azospirillum*, *Geobacter* and *Lentimicrobium*) were mainly correlated with pH and TOC. Most of these bacteria can carry out fermentation processes releasing CO₂ as a by-product (Sangeetha et al., 2022; Seifan et al., 2017). Under alkaline conditions CO₂ is converted into carbonate (Eq.1):

The presence of carbonate in solution may contribute to the immobilization of divalent metals such as Mn²⁺ or salts such as Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ as carbonate minerals (Eq. 2):

Table 3: Functional groups identified in the FTIR spectrums from **Fig. 8**.

Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)		Assignment	Reactors	References
Control	Sample			
3200–3350	3300	v (N–H), v (O–H), Amide A, water	Calcite	Gieroba et al., 2020
2920	2931.62	(CH ₂) lipids	Calcite	Battulga et al., 2020
1600–1700	1643.25	80% v (C=O), 20% v (C–N), τ (HOH), Amide I, water	Calcite	Battulga et al., 2020
1350–1200	1255.58	τ (N–H), v (C–N), τ (C=O), v (C–C), v (CH ₃), Amide III	Calcite	Gieroba et al., 2020
1732	1751.26	C=O in carboxylic acid groups	Barium Carbonate	Battulga et al., 2020
2920	2918.12	(CH ₂) lipids	Decanter	Battulga et al., 2020
2850–2860	2850.62	(CH ₂), lipids	Decanter	Gieroba et al., 2020
1730–1740	1730.04	(C=O), phospholipids	Decanter	Gieroba et al., 2020

1450–1400	1434.9	δ_{as} (CH ₃), δ_{as} (CH ₂), proteins, lipids	Decanter	Gieroba et al., 2020
3200–3350	3300	ν (N–H), ν (O–H), Amide A, water	Cascade	Gieroba et al., 2020
1634 – 1531	1649.04	80% ν (C=O), 20% ν (C–N), τ (HOH), Amide I, water	Cascade	Orhan-Yanikan et al., 2020
1350–1200	1259.44	τ (N–H), ν (C–N), τ (C=O), ν (C–C), ν (CH ₃), Amide III	Cascade	Gieroba et al., 2020

SEM-EDS suggests the presence of calcium carbonate minerals in the barium carbonate unit (**Fig. 7C**), the precipitation of these neoformed carbonate minerals along with the barium sulphate are mainly induced by the disassociation of the BaCO₃ (**Fig. 7C**) (Gomez-Arias et al., 2016) and the biomineralization processes may occur only on the surfaces of the cells. The cell wall contains functional groups that act as a nucleation site for metals and salts. Indeed, SEM images revealed bacterioforms covered by neoformed minerals composed of Ca, C and O, which may suggest the biomineralization of calcium carbonate on the cell walls (**Fig. 7D and E**). The IR spectra show a peak at 1751.26 cm⁻¹ (**Table 3, Supplementary Figure 5**), which is attributed to the carbonyl region. Elements such as Ca²⁺ can react with the C=O group to form various chelated complexes [Ca²⁺(CO)_y]_n (Qian et al., 2010). Interestingly, Microbially Induced CaCO₃ Precipitation (MICP) has not yet been applied to treat mine drainage containing heavy metals at pilot-scale (Torres-Aravena et al. 2018). However, MICP is observed in S5 despite no organic substrate for biostimulation was added in the treatment, which indicates that MICP occurred spontaneously due to the microbial activity, the high concentrations of TOC and the geochemistry processes within the S3, S4 and S5. The extent to which MICP has aided in the bioremediation of BDAS could be determined in future studies.

Consequences of bacterial proliferation in passive AMD treatment systems

The production of EPS by indigenous bacterial populations can be considered beneficial for the BDAS system, but only to a certain extent, as the production of EPS

may cause clogging of pores in water treatment systems due to the build-up of the precipitates on the biofilm and inside of the biofilm itself (Vanysacker et al., 2014). This process known as biofouling has been widely reported to affect active membrane systems, but it has not been documented in passive chemical systems (Sanchez, 2018; Sandlin et al., 2021).

As stated previously, many microorganisms (i.e., *Brevundimonas* sp., *Azospirillum* sp., and *Geobacter* sp.) in the units S2 and S3, can produce EPS that might contribute to the encapsulation of the chemical reagents (i.e., calcium carbonate and barium carbonate) acting as a barrier and inhibiting their disassociation. Indeed, the SEM-EDS images show that this process can take place in S3 (Fig. 8C-D). However, in S2 the precipitation of Fe^{3+} oxyhydroxysulphate (Fig. 8A-B) in the top of the matrix might contribute more to the inhibition of the reactivity of calcite.

Fig. 8. A) Schwertmannite-like minerals formed in the calcite reactor are highlighted in green and B) observed under SEM C) Barium reactor has been covered by biofilm-like structure, and the blue square area was examined by SEM (D) displaying the barium carbonate encapsulated by biofilm-like structure and bacterioforms.

Although no pathogenic test or genomic analysis were carried out in this study, opportunistic pathogens belonging to the genera *Coxiella*, *Legionella*, *Pseudomonas* and *Treponema* were detected in the BDAS system (**Supplementary Figure 6**). For instance, *Treponema* colonizes especially the decanter and cascade (Tukey test between S4/S5-S1/S2/S3; $p < 0.05$). The presence of these potential pathogens in the cascade, where the water exits the system, indicates the need to include a filtration process at the end of the system, such as biologically activated charcoal, to remove not only the inorganic particles that escape from the system but also the potential biological contamination (Li et al., 2017).

Conclusion

The chemistry of the AMD improves significantly throughout the BDAS system by alkalizing the water (~pH 8) and removing high concentrations of SO_4^{2-} (99% removal), Fe^{3+} (98%), and Ca^{2+} (75%) and minor elements such as Al^{3+} (98%) and Mn^{2+} (98%). The drastic changes in the physicochemical characteristics (e.g., increment of the TOC concentrations, and neutralization and alkalization processes) of the water shaped the bacterial communities present in each unit, inducing a significant differentiation between the inlet (AMD) and the rest of the system. The transition from chemolithotrophs such as *Acidiphilum* sp. and *Ferroplasma* sp., that populate the inlet (S1), to chemoorganotrophs such as *Geobacter* sp., *Hydrothermalis* sp., *Azospirillum* sp., that colonize the water treatment system (S2, S3, S4 and S5), is a clear example of this change. The biofilm observed throughout the system (except in the inlet) might induce the immobilization of heavy metals and salts, contributing to the treatment of the water. Indeed, it was observed that microbially induced CaCO_3 Precipitation (MICP) occurred spontaneously in the barium reactor (S3), decanter (S4) and cascade (S5) contributing to the immobilization of Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Mn^{2+} . To our knowledge, this is the first time that MICP is reported to promote the removal of metals and salts in passive AMD treatment systems. However, excessive amounts of biofilm might induce clogging and passivation of the alkaline reagent in the matrix inhibiting their reactivity and reducing treatment efficiency. While inorganic contamination is reduced by BDAS, we noted an increase of potential opportunistic pathogens (e.g., *Coxiella* sp., *Legionella* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp. and *Treponema* sp.)

through the system. The presence of these pathogens warrants the need to add an additional treatment step to reduce the levels of pathogenic microorganisms.

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Author contributions Statement

J. Castillo and A. Valverde: Conceptualization. J. Castillo, J. Alom, A. Matu, and A. Gomez-Arias: Methodology and Data curation. J. Castillo, J. Alom: Writing- Original draft preparation. A. Valverde, E.Cason, A. Matu, A. Gomez-Arias, and S. Cebekhulu: Reviewing and Editing. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Supplementary material

Supplementary Figure 1: Physicochemical parameters of each reactor in the BDAS treatment. The parameters are as follows; Temp: Temperature (°C), pH, EC: Electrical Conductivity (mS/cm), Eh: Oxidative Reduction Potential (mV), DO: Dissolved Oxygen (g/L), TOC: Total Organic Carbon (g/L).

Supplementary Figure 2: Elemental composition of each unit in BDAS displaying a decrease in metals and salts concentrations.

Supplementary Figure 3: Rarefied sequences before downstream analysis. S1, inlet; S2, calcite reactor; S3, barium reactor; S4, decanter reactor; S5, cascade.

Supplementary Figure 4: Prevalence and abundance of bacteria in the BDAS system.

Supplementary Figure 5. Fourier transmission infrared spectrum indicate peaks (see table 3) that corresponded to functional groups identified in each sample, namely from 1) – S2 (Calcite reactor), 2) – S3 (Barium reactor), 3) – S4 (Decanters), and 4) – S5 (Cascade).

Supplementary Figure 6: Spatial evolution of abundance of the potential pathogens throughout BDAS. S1, inlet; S2, calcite reactor; S3, barium reactor; S4, decanter reactor; S5, cascade.